

Ecotourism Destination Branding Analysis of Siargao Island, Surigao del Norte, Philippines

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Abstract

Brand equity is an important concept in analyzing the value of a destination brand as perceived by the tourists. This study seeks to determine some components of Siargao Island's brand equity as a tourism destination - specifically the brand awareness of ecotourism destination as well as the brand images associated with ecotourism destinations and that of Siargao Island. Using unaided recall to measure brand awareness, the study shows that Siargao is predominantly third (3rd) mentioned only among the respondents just behind El Nido and Boracay. Meanwhile, using thematic analysis, the study finds that the images associated with ecotourism destinations focused on themes such as aesthetic sceneries, tourist's activities, delicacies, and unwinding. Furthermore, respondents' images associated with Siargao are centered on themes such as tourist's activities, beautiful sceneries, food, and relaxation. Tourists like the accommodation, natural attractions, tourist's activities, and food in Siargao. However, they did not like the infrastructure, lack of medical facilities, safety, transportation, and the attitude of some locals. The tourists' ecotourism activities preferences focused highly on themes such as water activities and land activities. Tourists identified some unique features of Siargao like its natural attractions, people and entertainment. And finally, tourists' sources of images associated with Siargao centered on themes such as media organizations and word-of-mouth.

Keywords: *brand awareness, destination branding, destination images, ecotourism, Siargao Island.*

JEL Classification codes: *M30, M31, M37, M38, M39*

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Introduction

Destination branding involves marketing efforts that: (a) create a name, logo, or graphics to distinguish an ecotourism destination; (b) convey the promise of a memorable travel experience; (c) strengthen the connection between the destination and tourists; and (d) reduce costs and perceived risks in finding an ecotourism destination (Blain & Ritchie, 2005). This research study is anchored on Aaker's (1991) Consumer-Based Brand Equity (CBBE) model. Brand awareness is the first step in building brand equity, leading to brand image and perceived quality (Buil et al., 2013). Aaker emphasized that consumers must be exposed to a brand to develop awareness, which is a key dimension of brand equity (Keller, 2008) and reflects the strength of a destination brand

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in travel contexts. Unaided and aided brand recall are the most common measures of brand awareness.

Studies indicate that brand awareness significantly enhances destination brand loyalty in tourism (Bianchi & Pike, 2011; Pike & Bianchi, 2013; Srihadi et al., 2015). This study emphasizes the significance of destination branding in the ecotourism sector of the region. Most research has focused on other industries, making findings from abroad less relevant to diverse locations like the Philippines. Siargao Island, despite its popularity, still has untapped potential. Although tourist arrivals in the Philippines have increased, the country remains behind its neighbors (Choudhury, 2019). Effective ecotourism branding is essential for promoting Siargao as not only the surfing capital of the Philippines and Asia but also as a destination for adventurers and ecotourists.

Materials and Methods

Objectives of the Study

The main thrust of the study is to analyze the brand equity of Siargao Island as an ecotourism destination. Specifically, the study aims:

1. To determine the brand awareness on Siargao Island as an ecotourism destination;
2. To determine what images are associated with ecotourism destinations; and
3. To determine what images are associated with Siargao.

Research Design

This study employs a qualitative descriptive approach using personal and online in-depth interviews, as outlined by Koh & Owen (2000). The aim of qualitative research is to gain a deep understanding of specific occurrences within a particular group, rather than to describe the entire population. It indicates that data and meaning occur naturally from the research context. The research design uses thematic analysis to understand how individuals perceive a destination brand. Data was collected through open-ended interview questions.

Sampling Design

The research study focused on alumni of MSU-Commuters Hardcore, a recognized semi-academic organization at MSU-Main Campus. The target population consists of Millennials, individuals born between 1980 and 2000, who are characterized by their digital upbringing and technology-savviness (Kaife et al., 2012). This generation is also noted for their acceptance of non-traditional family structures and values (Andert, 2011). This study employed convenience sampling to identify respondents. This non-probability method relies on the availability and accessibility of participants, using readily accessible primary data without additional requirements.

The Respondents

The respondents of this study are alumni from MSU-Commuters Hardcore, a semi-academic organization at MSU-Main Campus recognized by the Division of Student Affairs. Out of 323 members from 2000 to 2019, approximately 50% are millennial professionals. The research specifically examines 50 members who have visited Siargao, comprising 25 males and 25 females. Most respondents are aged 21 to 25 (60%) and primarily single (92%). Table 1 outlines their demographic characteristics.

Table 1. Respondents' Demographic Characteristics

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	25	50
	Female	25	50
Age	b/w 21 and 25 years old	30	60
	b/w 26 and 30 years old	20	40
Civil Status	Single	46	92
	Married	4	8

Research Instrument

A semi-structured interview guide was developed and pilot tested with millennial marketing students from the MSU Main Campus to validate responses. Data from these pilot interviews were not included in the final analysis and were used to gather, measure, and analyze relevant information for the study.

Data Collection

The study was conducted from October to December 2019, involving interviews with 50 respondents. To address geographical challenges, the researcher employed both personal and online interviews. A semi-structured interview guide was used to prompt detailed accounts of participants' experiences in Siargao. Brand recall, specifically unaided recall, was used to evaluate brand awareness of Siargao. Respondents named ecotourism destinations, with their answers recorded in order from 1st to 5th mention.

Research Ethics

Prior to the conduct of the study, a letter was sent to the President of MSU-CHC for permission to use alumni members as participants and to obtain their personal details. Then, messages were sent via Messenger to ask respondents for their consent to participate in the research, considering convenience and location.

Data Analysis

To identify themes that support the study's objectives, thematic analysis was used. This method helps recognize patterns in qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2006) and is essential for various analyses. It is flexible, making it particularly suitable for the diverse nature of ecotourism destination branding. This study follows Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase framework for thematic analysis, which is considered a leading approach due to its clear methodology.

Commonly, researchers mistakenly use interview guide questions as themes (Clarke & Braun, 2013), leading to mere summarization rather than in-depth analysis. Braun and Clarke (2006) distinguish between two levels of themes: semantic, which examines superficial meanings, and latent, which explores deeper interpretations. This study examines respondents' perceptions of ecotourism destination branding, using both semantic analysis and latent analysis to uncover underlying themes. Data were collected from 60 respondents, including those who have and have not visited Siargao, and were transcribed verbatim. The focus is on the perceived brand equity of Siargao among tourists. The six-phase guide to thematic analysis by Braun and Clarke (2006) is a helpful framework for conducting this analysis.

Figure 1. Six-Phase of Thematic Analysis
 Source: Braun and Clarke (2006)

Results

Tourists' Ecotourism Destinations Brand Awareness

Brand awareness is crucial for establishing a destination brand, as a brand has no value without customer familiarity. Tourists create an awareness set before visiting an ecotourism destination, which then becomes a consideration set that guides their choices (Kashif et al., 2014). Respondents showed strong awareness of ecotourism destinations rich in natural resources and island formations. Key locations include El Nido, Boracay, Siargao, Coron, and Cebu, known for their beaches and lagoons. Other notable destinations are Davao, Camiguin, Bohol, and Batanes. El Nido, Boracay, Siargao, Coron, and Cebu were recognized as the top ecotourism spots. The majority of respondents identified El Nido as their top ecotourism destination, followed by Boracay, Siargao, and Coron in Palawan (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Frequency of Mention of Ecotourism Destinations by Respondents

Figure 2 shows that Siargao was identified as an ecotourism brand by 25 of 50 respondents. In terms of brand awareness, Siargao ranked third after El Nido, mentioned 41 times, and Boracay, mentioned 32 times. The top five ecotourism destinations include Siargao (21 mentions), Coron (14), and Cebu (11). Figure 3 illustrates tourists' brand awareness of these destinations.

Figure 3. Tourists' Ecotourism Destinations Brand Awareness Level

Tourists' Brand Images Associated with Ecotourism Destinations

Respondents were asked, "What do you enjoy about the ecotourism destination? (Tourist attractions/activities)" to gather insights on brand imagery. The coding process yielded responses from participants, creating various codes. Categorizing these codes revealed themes (see Table 2) relevant to the brand images of ecotourism destinations among respondents.

Table 2. Themes Generated from the Coding Process of Brand Images Associated with Ecotourism Destinations

Themes	Supporting Codes
Aesthetic Sceneries	Beaches, Sunset, Viewing deck, waves, nature, rock formation, islands
Tourist's Activities	Swimming, island hopping, caving, diving, snorkeling
Delicacies	Seafood, local food
Unwinding	Relaxing nature, peace of mind, sunbathing, joy-ride, peaceful nature

The analysis produced four themes regarding brand images associated with ecotourism destinations: aesthetic sceneries (e.g., beaches and waves); tourist activities (e.g., island hopping, caving, and swimming); delicacies (e.g., seafood, local food); and unwinding (e.g., joy ride, peace of mind).

Tourists' Images Associated with Siargao

The question, "What comes to your mind when you hear about Siargao?" illuminated the brand images the respondents have of Siargao. The coding analysis of participant responses generated several codes. These codes were organized into themes (see Table 3) that reveal the images of Siargao as perceived by the respondents.

Table 3. Themes Generated from the Coding Process of Tourists' Images Associated with Siargao

Themes	Supporting Codes
Tourist's Activities	Surfing, Island hopping, swimming
Beautiful Sceneries	Beaches, Islands, coconuts, Islets
Food	Seafood, food
Relaxation	Unwinding, joy-ride, Islander life

The analysis of respondents revealed four main themes: (1) tourist activities, (2) beautiful scenery, (3) food, and (4) relaxation. These themes showcase the perceptions of Siargao from visitors.

Things That Tourists Like about Siargao

Respondents shared their preferences about Siargao as an ecotourism destination. Most appreciated the accommodations offered by homestays, hotels, and resorts, as well as the seafood, beaches, lagoons, surfing, and island hopping activities. Understanding these preferences is crucial for tourism operators to create suitable ecotourism packages. The coding analysis of participant responses generated several codes. This analysis identified key themes (refer to Table 4) related to what tourists enjoy about Siargao.

Table 4. Themes Generated from the Coding Process of the Things They Like About Siargao

Themes	Supporting Codes
Accommodations	Homestay, Hotel, Resort
Natural Attractions	Beaches, Lagoons
Tourist's Activities	Surfing, Island Hopping
Food	Seafood

Based on the analysis, the codes produced four themes for the things that the tourists like about Siargao. These themes are: (1) accommodation; (2) natural attractions; (3) tourist's activities; and (4) food as shown in Table 4.

Things That Tourists Dislike about Siargao

Despite Siargao's natural attractions and good accommodations, tourists noted several drawbacks, including a lack of medical facilities, no lifeguards, instances of catcalling, limited transportation options, and unfinished road construction. The coding analysis revealed only a few responses from the participants. However, it produced relevant codes and themes, shown in Table 5, highlighting what tourists dislike about Siargao.

Table 5. Themes Generated from the Coding Process the Things They Didn't Like About Siargao

Themes	Supporting Codes
Infrastructure	Unfinished roads
Lack of Medical Facilities	Lack of hospitals, accident
Safety	No life guards
Transportation	Difficulty of commuting, few public motor vehicles
Attitude of Some Locals	Catcalling, disrespectful, crowd

The analysis identified five main complaints tourists had about Siargao: (1) poor infrastructure; (2) limited medical facilities; (3) safety concerns; (4) transportation issues; and (5) the attitudes of some locals.

Tourists' Ecotourism Activities Preferences

The International Ecotourism Society defines ecotourism as responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment and supports local communities (TIES, 2015). Identifying tourist attractions and activities is essential for ecotourism destinations. Siargao, known as the "Surfing Capital of the Philippines," offers stunning attractions beyond surfing, including white-sand beaches, lagoons, caves, coral reefs, waterfalls, and a large mangrove forest reserve. The coding analysis of respondents' answers led to several codes. Grouping these codes revealed themes (see Table 6) that highlight the ecotourism activities preferred by tourists in Siargao.

Table 6. Themes Generated from the Coding Process of the Tourists' Ecotourism Activities Preferences

Themes	Supporting Codes
Water Activities	Swimming, Island hopping, surfing
Land Activities	Caving, joy-ride

According to the analysis, the codes produced two themes for ecotourism activities preferred by tourists in Siargao. These themes are: (1) water activities (e.g., swimming, island hopping, and surfing) and (2) land activities (e.g., caving and joyrides).

Siargao's Unique Features

To differentiate itself, an ecotourism destination must offer unique features in its packages. Pappu et al. (2005) highlight that behavioral loyalty is shown through repeat purchases, while brand loyalty can be both behavioral and attitudinal. Understanding Siargao's uniqueness is crucial for analyzing tourist choices. Respondents were asked, "What makes Siargao different from other ecotourism destinations?" Their answers were recorded for further insight. The coding analysis of participant responses generated various codes. This coding process identified themes (see Table 7) that highlight the unique features of Siargao.

Table 7. Themes Generated from the Coding Process of the Unique Features of Siargao

Themes	Supporting Codes
Natural Attractions	Unique beaches, surfing, island formations
People	Locals
Entertainment	G.L. Night life

Based on the analysis, the codes produced three themes for the unique features of Siargao as shared by the respondents. These themes are: (1) natural attractions (e.g. unique beaches, island formations, and surfing), (2) People (e.g. locals) and (3) entertainment (e.g. G.L. night life).

Tourists' Sources of Images Associated with Siargao

With increasing competition in the tourism industry, it's essential to implement promotional strategies to reach potential and existing customers (Hill, 2016). To understand the images associated with Siargao, we asked tourists, "Where or from whom did you hear about Siargao?"

The coding analysis of respondents' feedback generated several codes. Organizing these codes revealed themes (see Table 8) that highlight tourists' sources of brand awareness about Siargao.

Table 8. Themes Generated from the Coding Process of the Tourists' Sources of Images Associated with Siargao

Themes	Supporting Codes
Media Organizations	TV/Movie Print Ads (e.g. Magazine and Newspaper) Social Media (e.g. Facebook)
Word-of-Mouth	Friends, Family

The analysis identified two key sources of brand awareness for Siargao among respondents: (1) media organizations (TV, movies, print ads, and social media) and (2) word-of-mouth from family and friends.

Discussion

El Nido, located in the Palawan Islands, is a major tourist destination in the Philippines, featuring 45 islands and renowned limestone cliffs. It attracts both local and foreign tourists, especially during holidays, but has recently become less known to international travelers. The area is famous for its beautiful beaches, clear waters, and lush jungles, perfect for adventures (Ololofm, 2019). Boracay, on the other hand, is an island paradise known for its stunning white sand beaches and clear blue waters. Situated off the northwest corner of Panay Island in Aklan Province, Boracay is a top choice for beach lovers and ranks among the world's best beach destinations, competing with renowned spots in the Caribbean, South Pacific, and neighboring Southeast Asian countries. Boracay offers a variety of activities, including water sports like sailing, windsurfing, snorkeling, diving, and jet skiing, which tourists enjoy. The nightlife is vibrant too, with bars, restaurants, and bazaars open until dawn (Binbin, 2020). While respondents associate ecotourism with natural resources and islands, awareness of Siargao as an ecotourism destination is lower compared to other well-known locations. Thus, Siargao as an ecotourism destination brand must focus on the brand awareness level by increasing its presence in the minds of the tourists.

The aesthetic sceneries of an ecotourism destination are mainly associated with natural tourist attractions. Most of the respondents think of beaches, sunsets, waves, viewing decks among others when it comes to an ecotourism destination. Clearly, the brand image associated with ecotourism destinations is highly centered on beaches. Indeed, aesthetic scenery of an ecotourism destination is one of the tourists' considerations when visiting a specific ecotourism destination brand. Tourist activities in ecotourism destinations mainly include water-related experiences like island hopping, swimming, diving, and snorkeling. These activities are essential to the tourism industry, as they attract potential visitors eager to explore what each destination has to offer. When considering ecotourism destinations, the importance of local delicacies cannot be overlooked. Food is a vital aspect of Filipino culture, fostering bonds among family and friends. As Filipino delicacies gain recognition in the culinary world (Escalona, 2018), ecotourism packages should include not only activities and scenery but also delicious local cuisine to attract visitors. When someone wants to unwind, they seek relaxation and relief from their burdens. Emphasizing "unwinding" in the brand image of ecotourism destinations highlights peaceful experiences in nature like joyrides and sunbathing. Visitors often look for places to relax and enjoy solitude, so it's vital for ecotourism spots to focus on this theme to enhance their appeal.

Tourist activities in Siargao primarily revolve around the sea, especially surfing, swimming, and island hopping. The island is renowned for its surfing, particularly the famous Cloud 9 wave, and is recognized as the surfing capital of the Philippines and Asia. The Annual Siargao International Surfing Cup further enhances its global reputation. In addition to surfing, island hopping and swimming attract those less interested in surfing. Offering diverse activities is crucial for ecotourism, as it appeals to both potential and returning visitors, encouraging them to explore what Siargao has to offer and enhancing their overall vacation experience. Siargao is renowned for its stunning natural features, including beautiful beaches, islands, and coconut palms. Most respondents associate Siargao's brand with these elements, particularly its exceptional beaches, such as General Luna Beach, Daku Island, and Naked Island. Aside from surfing at Cloud 9, visitors can enjoy picturesque spots among the coconut palms for relaxation and photography. Siargao's breathtaking landscapes significantly impact tourists' choices when selecting ecotourism destinations. Recognized as one of the best islands in Asia and featured in Conde Nast Traveler's list of the world's top 20 holiday spots for 2020, Siargao is a must-visit for nature lovers seeking beauty and tranquility. People love to eat, especially unique foods. In Siargao, seafood is a major attraction, mentioned 40 times by respondents in a recent survey. When visiting, tourists should definitely include food sampling in their itineraries, as trying new dishes is part of the travel experience. Siargao is also developing as an ecotourism hub, with investments in resorts, restaurants, and hotels, according to the Tourism Office of General Luna. Food is vital in drawing visitors and is essential to the ecotourism industry. Relaxation in Siargao is tied to experiences that help tourists unwind and think positively through joyrides and island life. As an ecotourism hub, Siargao offers a tranquil environment that promotes relaxation. The Journal of Environmental Psychology highlights humans' innate desire to connect with nature, known as biophilia, noting that just 40 seconds of viewing natural scenery can relax the brain (Johansson, 2018). In Siargao, themes of unwinding, islander life, and joyrides were mentioned 30, 1, and 10 times respectively, indicating that tourists visit to relax and rejuvenate.

Respondents highlighted their positive experiences in Siargao, viewing it as a top ecotourism destination. They particularly enjoyed the accommodations, such as homestays, hotels, and resorts, as well as the local seafood, beaches, lagoons, surfing, and island hopping activities. Understanding these preferences is essential for tourism operators to create appealing ecotourism packages. Accommodation in Siargao primarily consists of private establishments like homestays, hotels, and resorts. Many local homes have been converted into homestays, providing extra income for residents. According to the Tourism Office of General Luna, which includes the famous Cloud 9 surf spot, there are over 300 accommodation options in the area, with homestays being the most common. Thus, finding suitable lodging is essential for visitors to this ecotourism destination. Tourists are drawn to Siargao's natural attractions, particularly its beaches and lagoons. Popular tourist activities in Siargao primarily revolve around the sea, especially surfing and island hopping, which received 35 and 45 mentions from respondents. Ecotourism providers should prioritize these activities for an optimal visitor experience. Additionally, food, particularly seafood, plays a significant role, with 30 mentions indicating that dining is a key motivation for tourists. According to the World Tourism Organization, travelers spend about one-third of their holiday budget on food (Coppola, 2016). Clearly, seafood is a major draw for visitors to Siargao.

Despite its natural beauty, accommodations, and activities, Siargao has drawbacks that some tourists dislike, such as a lack of medical facilities, no lifeguards, instances of catcalling, limited transportation options, and ongoing road construction. Infrastructure is vital for economic growth (Puentes, 2015), as it aids in delivering services to tourists and businesses. Therefore, prioritizing infrastructure development in Siargao is essential to attract more tourists and investments. Medical facilities in Siargao, including the hospital, have raised concerns among visitors. Some respondents highlighted a lack of services during emergencies, though most reported no serious incidents during

their stay. The issue gained attention on social media, particularly when broadcaster Karen Davila shared her disappointment regarding insufficient medical support after her son's accident in 2018. Similarly, Yeng Constantino expressed frustration when her husband suffered an injury while cliff diving, criticizing a doctor for inadequate response. Surigao del Norte officials attributed the lack of services to limited funding, as Dapa is a 5th-class municipality. However, national government intervention has resulted in budget allocations to improve medical facilities in Siargao, emphasizing the importance of such resources for ensuring tourist safety in the ecotourism industry. Safety in Siargao hinges on personnel, especially lifeguards. As tourists increasingly prioritize safety (LeJune, 2017), ensuring their protection should be the top concern for ecotourism operators. Lifeguards are essential at attractions and activities for quick response to accidents. Transportation in Siargao mainly relies on motorcycles and multicabs, with limited public options leading to some challenges. Tourists can rent mopeds or motorbikes for \$7 to \$8 per day, plus gas, so budgeting around \$10 daily is advisable. Tricycle rides within the town cost about \$1 to \$2 for 15 minutes (Jackson, 2019). Driving is beneficial for exploring Siargao's spread-out attractions, and renting a motorbike can be more economical than public transport. While a few incidents of catcalling and disrespect were reported, most visitors did not experience such behavior. It's crucial for locals to maintain a welcoming attitude to uphold Siargao's reputation and encourage repeat visits. Enhancing the overall tourist experience can boost satisfaction levels.

Tourists in Siargao enjoy a variety of ecotourism activities, including both water and land pursuits. Water activities like surfing, swimming, and island hopping attract visitors, with many seeking experiences beyond surfing, even if they find it challenging. This makes Siargao appealing to both surfers and non-surfers. On land, adventurous activities such as caving and joy rides are also popular. Siargao offers much more than just its reputation as the "Surfing Capital of the Philippines." Notably, all respondents reported enjoying the ecotourism activities in Siargao, indicating that even non-surfers had a positive experience. This showcases the abundance of tourist spots and activities available on the island.

Siargao's unique features, as highlighted by respondents, include its natural attractions—such as unique beaches, island formations, and surfing—along with its local people and vibrant nightlife in General Luna. Tourists often enjoy a problem-free experience, with the island's appeal centered around its natural beauty and adventures. The locals significantly contribute to Siargao's charm, with their traditions and interactions enhancing the overall visitor experience. Additionally, the nightlife in General Luna, including bar hopping and live music, is a major draw, offering a lively atmosphere after sunset. Siargao consistently provides fun and excitement, making it a popular ecotourism destination.

The brand awareness of Siargao among respondents primarily comes from media organizations (e.g., TV, movies, print ads, and social media) and word-of-mouth communication from family and friends. Media plays a crucial role in delivering advertising messages (O'Guinn et al., 2012). Social media was the most significant source of brand awareness, mentioned 45 times, followed by TV and movies at 35 times, and print ads at 25 times. This highlights the importance of media organizations in promoting Siargao as an ecotourism destination. Word-of-mouth also significantly impacts Siargao's brand image, with family cited 20 times and friends 40 times. Satisfied tourists often share their positive experiences, but word-of-mouth can also spread negative information.

Conclusion

Consumer-based brand equity research is crucial to branding, highlighting brand awareness as the first step in building brand image and loyalty (Cai, 2002). Siargao, an ecotourism destination, currently has lower brand awareness compared to its competitors, who benefit from longer-

established promotional efforts. Customer brand awareness is essential for perceiving brand quality (Buil et al., 2013) and influences customers' perceptions (Keller, 1993). According to Aaker (1991), awareness is necessary for developing brand associations, which Keller (1993) states are key to understanding a brand's quality.

Brand awareness for ecotourism destinations mainly highlights El Nido, Boracay, and Coron in Palawan, with Siargao ranking third. This indicates that Siargao is less recognized than these popular spots. To attract more visitors, Siargao should focus on boosting its visibility among tourists. Ecotourism destination images often highlight beautiful scenery, tourist activities, local delicacies, and relaxation. Siargao, in particular, showcases these themes, emphasizing its appeal as an ecotourism hotspot where visitors can unwind and enjoy activities in a pristine environment. Notably, images of Siargao focus on surfing, along with beaches, islands, seafood, island hopping, and relaxation.

Tourists enjoy the accommodations, natural attractions, activities, and food in Siargao, which offers a variety of options like homestays, hotels, beaches, surfing, and island hopping. However, they are dissatisfied with the infrastructure, limited medical facilities, safety issues, transportation, and some locals' attitudes. This feedback highlights the need for Siargao to improve its amenities and services to better meet tourists' needs. Tourists in Siargao prefer a variety of ecotourism activities, mainly focusing on water and land options. Island hopping and swimming stand out as the most popular choices, indicating that Siargao caters to both surfing and non-surfing enthusiasts. The island's unique charm lies in its natural attractions, local culture, and entertainment, offering experiences that are exclusive to Siargao. Siargao's image is shaped by media organizations and word-of-mouth, particularly through social media and personal recommendations. These channels play a significant role in promoting Siargao as an ecotourism destination.

Considering that Siargao ranks third in mentions among respondents, crafting robust social media strategies to showcase the stunning imagery of Siargao can greatly elevate its profile. This will not only boost brand awareness but also attract potential tourists eager to explore Siargao as a premier ecotourism destination.

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